

IKKINCHI TUR BUZILADIGAN PARABOLO-GIPERBOLIK TENGLAMA UCHUN NOLOKAL SHARTLI CHEGARAVIY MASALA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishda ikkinchi tur buziladigan parabolo-giperbolik tenglama uchun nolokal shartli chegaraviy masala tadqiq qilingan. Masala yechimi giperbolik sohada ikkinchi tur buziladigan giperbolik tenglama uchun Koshi masalasi yechimidan foydalanib qidirilgan. Parabolik shada esa Riman –Liuvill ma'nosidagi kasr tartibli hosila ishtirok etgan parabolik tenglama uchun birinchi chegaraviy masala yechimidan foydalanib topilgan.

Аннотация. В данной работе исследуется нелокальная краевая задача для вырождающегося параболо-гиперболического уравнения второго рода. Решение задачи искалось с использованием решения задачи Коши для вырождающегося гиперболического уравнения второго рода в гиперболической области. В параболической области решение было найдено с использованием решения первой краевой задачи для параболического уравнения, содержащего производную дробного порядка в смысле Римана-Лиувилля.

Abstract. In this paper, we investigate a nonlocal boundary value problem for a second-kind degenerate parabolic-hyperbolic equation. The solution to the problem is obtained using the solution to the Cauchy problem for a second-kind degenerate hyperbolic equation in the hyperbolic domain. In the parabolic domain, the solution is derived using the first boundary value problem for a parabolic equation that includes a fractional derivative in the Riemann-Liouville sense.

Kalit so'zlar: parabolo-giperbolik tenglama, aralash soha, nolokal shartli chegaraviy masala, Koshi masalasi, birinchi chegaraviy masala.

Ключевые слова: уравнение параболо-гиперболического типа, смешанная область, нелокальная краевая задача, задача Коши, первая краевая задача

Keywords: parabolic-hyperbolic type equation, mixed domain, nonlocal boundary value problem, Cauchy problem, first boundary value problem.

Masalaning qo'yilishi. Ushbu

$$0 = \begin{cases} L_1(u) \equiv u_{xx} + D_{0y}^\alpha u, & y > 0 \\ L_2(u) \equiv u_{xx} + yu_{yy} + (-n + 1/2)u_y = 0, & y < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

tenglamani $D = D_1 \cup D_2 \cup AB$ sohada qaraylik, bu yerda D_1 quyidagi chiziqlar $AA_1 : x = 0$, $A_1B_1 : y = 1$, $BB_1 : x = 1$, $AB : y = 0$ bilan chegaralangan soha, D_2 - (1) tenglamaning xarakteristikalari $AB : y = 0$, $AC : x - 2\sqrt{-y} = 0$, $BC : x + 2\sqrt{-y} = 1$ bilan chegaralangan soha, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, D_{0x}^α - α kasr tartibli Riman -Liuvill ma'nosidagi hosila

$$D_{0x}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_0^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1.$$

Masala A. Quyidagi shartlarni va (1) tenglamani qanoatlantiruvchi $u(x, y)$ funksiya topilsin:

$$y^{1-\alpha}u(x, y) \in C(\overline{D_1}), u(x, y) \in C(\overline{D_2});$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow -0} u(x, y) = \lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{1-\alpha}u(x, y), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1; \quad (2)$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow -0} (-y)^\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial y} [u - A_{-n+1/2}^-(\tau)] = \lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{1-\alpha} [y^{1-\alpha}u(x, y)]_y, \quad 0 < x < 1; \quad (3)$$

$$u|_{AA_0} = \varphi_0(y), \quad u|_{BB_0} = \varphi_1(y), \quad 0 < y < 1; \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{d^{n+1}}{dx^{n+1}} u[\theta_0(x)] = \sum_{k=0}^{2n} e_k(x) \frac{d^k}{dx^k} u(x, 0) + l(x) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \Big|_{y=+0} + f(x), \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad (5)$$

$$\tau^{(m)}(0) = 0, \quad m = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 2n, \quad (6)$$

bu yerda $\varphi_0(y)$, $\varphi_1(y)$, $e_k(x)$, $k = \overline{0, 2n}$, $f(x)$ – berilgan funksiyalar, $\theta_0(x)$ – AC xarakteristika bilan $E(x, 0)$ nuqtadan chiquvchi xarakteristikaning kesishish nuqtasi, $\tau(x) = u(x, 0)$,

$$A_{-n+1/2}^-(\tau) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{n!(2n-k)!2^{2k}(-y)^{k/2}}{k!(n-k)!(2n)!} \left[\tau^{(k)}(x-2\sqrt{-y}) + (-1)^k \tau^{(k)}(x+2\sqrt{-y}) \right].$$

Asosiy qism. D_2 sohada $L_2(u) = 0$ tenglama uchun

$$u(x, 0) = \tau(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow -0} (-y)^{1/2-n} [u - A_{-n+1/2}^-(\tau)]'_y = \nu(x), \quad 0 < x < 1$$

boshlang'ich shartlar bilan qo'yilgan ko'rinishi o'zgargan Koshi masalasining yechimi [1]

$$u(x, y) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{n!(2n-k)!2^{2k-1}(-y)^{k/2}}{k!(n-k)!(2n)!} \left[\tau^{(k)}(x-2\sqrt{-y}) + (-1)^k \tau^{(k)}(x+2\sqrt{-y}) \right] +$$

$$- \frac{2(-1)^n(2n)!}{(n!)^2} (-y)^{n+1/2} \int_0^1 \nu \left[x - 2\sqrt{-y}(1-2z) \right] [z(1-z)]^n dz \quad (7)$$

dan iborat. Qo'yilgan masalaning D_2 sohadagi yechimini (7) funksiya sifatida qidiramiz. (7) funksiyaning $\theta_0(x)$ nuqtadagi qiymatini yozib olamiz

$$u[\theta_0(x)] = u(x/2, -x^2/16) = \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{n!(2n-k)!x^k}{2k!(n-k)!(2n)!} \left[\tau^{(k)}(0) + (-1)^k \tau^{(k)}(x) \right] +$$

$$- \frac{2(-1)^n(2n)!}{(n!)^2} (x^2/16)^{n+1/2} \int_0^1 \nu(xz) [z(1-z)]^n dz.$$

Oxirgi ifodadan $n+1$ marta hosila olamiz

$$\frac{d^{n+1}}{dx^{n+1}} u[\theta(x)] = (-1)^n \frac{n!}{(2n)!} x^n \tau^{(2n+1)}(x) - 4^{2n} (-1)^n \frac{(2n)!}{n!} x^n \nu(x).$$

$\frac{d^n}{dx^n} u[\theta(x)]$ funksiyaning qiymatini (5) shartga qo'yib $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalar orasidagi birinchi munosabatni olamiz

$$\begin{aligned} & (-1)^n \frac{n!}{(2n)!} x^n \tau^{(2n+1)}(x) - \sum_{k=0}^{2n} e_k(x) \tau^{(k)}(x) = \\ & = \left[l(x) + 4^{2n} (-1)^n \frac{(2n)!}{n!} x^n \right] \nu(x) + f(x), \quad 0 < x < 1. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Endi D_1 sohadan asosiy funksional munosabatlarni olish maqsadida $L_1(u) = 0$ tenglamani $y^{1-\alpha}$ ifodaga ko'paytirishdan hosil bo'lgan tenglikda (2)- (4) shartlarni e'tiborga olib $y \rightarrow +0$ da limitga o'tamiz [qarang Gekkiyeva]. Natijada,

$$\tau''(x) - \Gamma(\alpha + 1)\nu(x) = 0, \quad \lim_{y \rightarrow 0+} D_{0y}^{\alpha-1} \varphi_0(y) = \tau(0), \quad \lim_{y \rightarrow 0+} D_{0y}^{\alpha-1} \varphi_1(y) = \tau(1) \quad (9)$$

munosabatlarni olamiz. Demak, Trikomi masalasi, yechimga ega bo'lish ma'nosida, {(6), (8), (9)} tenglamalar sistemasiga ekvivalent. Chunki, agar bu sistemadan $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalarni bir qiymatli topilsa, Trikomi masalasining yechimi D_2 sohada (7) formula bilan, D_1 sohada esa $L_1 u = 0$ tenglama uchun birinchi chegaraviy masalaning yechimi [3]

$$u(x, y) = \int_0^y \varphi_0(\eta) G_\xi(x, y, 0, \eta) d\eta - \int_0^y \varphi_1(\eta) G_\xi(x, y, a, \eta) d\eta + \int_0^a \tau(\xi) G(x, y, \xi, 0) d\xi$$

sifatida topiladi, bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} G(x, y, \xi, \eta) &= (y - \eta)^{\beta-1} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \left(e_{1,\beta}^{1,\beta} \left(-\frac{|x - \xi + 2na|}{(y - \eta)^\beta} \right) - e_{1,\beta}^{1,\beta} \left(-\frac{|x + \xi + 2na|}{(y - \eta)^\beta} \right) \right), \quad \beta = \alpha / 2, \\ e_{\alpha,\beta}^{\mu,\delta}(z) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\delta - \beta n) \Gamma(\alpha n + \mu)}, \quad \alpha > \beta. \end{aligned}$$

Teorema. Agar berilgan funksiyalar ushbu

$$\begin{aligned} & y^{1-\alpha} \varphi_0(y), y^{1-\alpha} \varphi_1(y) \in C[0,1] \cap C^1[0,1], \\ & x^{-n} e_k(x), \quad x^{-n} l(x), \quad x^{-n} f(x) \in C[0,1], k = 0, 2n, \end{aligned}$$

shartlarni qanoatlantirsa, u holda A masala yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi.

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